

Enlace de Agentes de Pastoral Indígena (EAPI, Network of Indigenous Ministry Agents)

also known as "Indigenous Theology in Mexico", "Indigenous Catholicisms in Mexico"

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Entry tags: Mesoamerican Religions, Native American (North American) Religions, Catholic, Religious Group, Syncretic Religions, Subaltern Religion, Zapotec Religion, Tarascan religion, Mayan Religions, Mixtec Religion, Christianity of the Global South, Liberation Theology, Indigenous tribal, Indigenous Theology

Growing out of the progressive Liberation Theology movement, groups of clergy and laypeople throughout Mexico organized EAPI in 1990 as a loose organization for sharing best practices, promoting organic indigenous theology, and questioning how to make the official Catholic Church more indigenous and more responsive to indigenous needs.

Date Range: 1990 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Mexico

Region tags:

Mexico, current national boundaries

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Eben Levey, "From Liberation Theology to Teología India: The Progressive Catholic Church in Southern Mexico, 1954-1994," Dissertation, University of Maryland - College Park, 2021.

– Source 2: EAPI annual meeting documents, privately published and circulated among members

– Source 3: Paja Faudree, *Singing For the Dead*, 2013

Reference: Valtierra Zamudio, Jorge. *La Pastoral Indígena Del Siglo Xxi En El Sur De México: Misioneros, Sociedad Civil Y Gobernanza*. Universidad Autónoma "Benito Juárez" de Oaxaca, 2019.

– Source 1: Jorge Valtierra Zamudio. *La pastoral indígena del siglo xxi en el sur de México: Misioneros, sociedad civil y gobernanza*. Universidad Autónoma "Benito Juárez" de Oaxaca. isbn: 978-607-9061-81-4

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: cenami.org

– Source 1 Description: Website for CENAMI, the Centro Nacional de Ayuda a Misiones Indígenas. Now an independent civil association, CENAMI was the episcopate's primary vehicle for organizing indigenous ministry within the Mexican Catholic Church. The CENAMI staff are closely involved with EAPI.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/pastoralindigenaceps/>

– Source 2 Description: Dimensión de pastoral indígena, Comisión Episcopal de Pastoral Social

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://issuu.com/caritasmexicana/docs/futepin>

– Source 1 Description: Fundamentos teológicos de la pastoral indígena en México, Comisión Episcopal para Indígenas

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– I don't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Generally by self-identified indigenous ethnicity OR as an ally of indigenous Catholic movements

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: This is complicated, and widely varied. EAPI does not condone violence, yet there has been a great deal of violence in indigenous Mexico by indigenous Catholics targeting Protestant and Evangelical converts who have recused themselves from community religious life. Violence has ranged from social shunning to physical attacks to arson and exile from communities. The best work on this is: Marroquín, Enrique. *El conflicto religioso: Oaxaca, 1976-1992*. México, CDMX: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2007.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: This has happened in communities where there are EAPI members, but is not universal. It is not condoned by EAPI.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

Notes: This has happened in communities where there are EAPI members, but is not universal. It is not condoned by EAPI.

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

Notes: This has happened in communities where there are EAPI members, but is not universal. It is not condoned by EAPI.

↳ Apostates are physically marked as such (e.g. branding, mutilation):

– No

↳ Apostates are executed:

– Yes

Notes: This has happened in communities where there are EAPI members, but is not universal. It is not condoned by EAPI.

↳ Apostates are publicly executed:

– Yes

Notes: This has happened in communities where there are EAPI members, but is not universal. It is not condoned by EAPI.

↳ Other corporal punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Collectively administered bodily harm has happened in communities where there are EAPI members, but is not universal. It is not condoned by EAPI.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Approximately 300 people attended the national meeting of EAPI in winter 2017, held in a community near Acaxochitlán, Hidalgo. Membership numbers vary considerably and are often quite dependent on clergy recruiting parishioners to be active participants in indigenous ministry. As such, there is no formal membership to speak of

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: EAPI is officially recognized by the Catholic Church in Mexico.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: Generally the parish priest, although there are certainly lay leaders who can be more or less active in certain parishes and communities.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: The bishop of each participating diocese sanctions and provides (modest) resources for diocesan meetings of EAPI. Some bishops are more involved than others.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Technically, the head of the Episcopal Commission of Social Ministry (Comisión Episcopal de la pastoral social) of the Mexican Bishops Conference (CEB) oversees EAPI.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: There are executive board members, mostly clergy, who plan and oversee EAPI activities and meetings for each year.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: The head of the Episcopal Commission on Social Ministry is often a three year term, Mexican bishops choose the next commission head.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible (Catholic) and indigenous codices from the early colonial period (sixteenth century)

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Indigenous community collective memory informs and structures religious practice and rituals - devotions to saints, offerings, ceremonies in sacred spaces (mountain tops, caves, rivers, depends on the community).

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Varies considerably from community to community. Many communities have origin stories of when their patron saint appeared.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: But they are interpretable

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: Although this was a contentious issue in Catholicism. The rise of Christian Base Communities (CEBs) in Latin America encouraged progressive clergy and lay activists to interpret the scripture in light of community reality and history. EAPI and CEBs share that methodology of lay empowerment to discuss scripture and indigenous religious history to interpret and act in the present.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Catholic clergy, lay catechists

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: For EAPI members, this includes the codices of the early colonial period that describe indigenous religious practices that preceded the arrival of Hernán Cortes and the Spanish colonizers.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Catholic churches and chapels, devotional buildings, and precolonial indigenous religious structures

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Only in precolonial ruins

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Home altars are quite important for devotion to particular saints and to communicate with deceased family

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Often in front of the church or chapel

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Shrines to popular saints and religious figures

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

Notes: This can range from material items and food/drink that have spiritual meaning in indigenous religious practices to glyphs and artwork that come from the precolonial indigenous societies - all in addition to Catholic religious iconography that indigenous communities have adopted as their own.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: All of the above, but with different meanings in different indigenous spaces. What makes EAPI distinct is the deliberate use of precolonial religious iconography, imagery, and practice combined with Catholic practices.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrimages vary by individual and family devotion. In southern Mexico, there may be pilgrimages to the Virgin of Guadalupe and/or to the Virgin of Juquila or other religious figures and shrines.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: In general, indigenous Catholics believe that ancestors remain in contact with the human world after death. Although there is some scholarly disagreement as to whether celebrations like Day of the Dead are European or precolonial in origin, offerings for the dead to assist in their journey are common in household and graveside shrines.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:
– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– Yes [specify]: Heaven, hell, and on this world as the spirits of the dead remain in contact with the human world

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: If we conceive of sacrifices as offerings - food, drink, money - then yes.

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– No

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Favorite items and foodstuffs - graveside

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In central Mexico, and among EAPI members/indigenous Catholics more broadly, the conception of the Christian God may actually be a duality of father god (tota'tzin in Náhuatl) and mother god (often the Virgin of Guadalupe, tonan'tzin).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Christian God, although exists alongside mother God in a duality.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– No

Notes: Generally not, although some more conservative Catholics believe in God's punishment. If anything, punishment is god or saint's failure to act as an intercessory likely because the devotee did not give proper devotion or offerings.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although gods may not necessarily be hungry for food so much as for devotion and attention. Promises in return for intercession include devotional prayer,

donations, pilgrimage, and/or more mundane offerings such as food and drink.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Patron saints and other religious figures as intercessories rely on devotional offerings in order that they act in the world on behalf of the devotee.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer and devotional offerings and promises

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Indigenous Catholics tend to believe that the deceased remain in contact with the living. Everyday altars at home are maintained in memory of and with offerings for the deceased. The Day of the Dead celebrates the moment in which the dead are closest to the living.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

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- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - No
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: These supernatural beings can be a mix of Catholic saints and precolonial deities.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, both official and "popular," have a long history of appearing to individuals, often asking for a shrine or a devotion in return for protection and/or intercession.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: But there is specialization - patron saints of different places, sectors, jobs,

people, processes.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is generally restricted to not interceding on behalf of or protecting the devotees as a result of insufficient devotion/offering.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Precolonial societies sometimes have family relations, but it varies widely among and between indigenous ethnic groups.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Sort of. Different deities and different patron saints will have more or less

important meanings for individuals, families, and communities.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Patron saints have particular fields of specialty, and precolonial deities often are restricted to different natural phenomena

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the Christian god is all-knowing, there is certainly supernatural monitoring.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Indigenous communities in Mexico are known to have entwined civil and religious community responsibilities that are geared toward maintaining community governance, social relations, and unity. Oaxacan indigenous intellectuals such as Floriberto Díaz and Juan José Rendón have conceptualized these practices, encompassing morality, ethics, and religious practice, as "comunalidad." Comunalidad is both both religious and secular, monitored from above and via everyday interactions of community members.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Church, chapel, and/or natural phenomena that have spiritual or sacred meaning for particular communities.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Religious art and objects, depictions and representations of saints, precolonial art and architecture.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as Catholicism is concerned with the sanctity of human life, yes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as Catholicism is concerned with the sanctity of human life, yes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as Catholicism is concerned with the sanctity of human life, yes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Premarital sex tends to be a Catholic concern, although indigenous and popular Catholics are far less concerned about it than the Church hierarchy. Church sanctioned marriage rates tend to be lower in indigenous communities as marriage is an expensive religious celebration. In lieu of marriage, people can and do live together in long-term domestic partnerships that are often recognized within communities as similar to or equal to marriage.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Patron saints in popular and indigenous Catholicisms are concerned that devotees fulfill their devotional promises in return for intercession.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: In Christian theology, sloth is a sin

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Witchcraft, healing, and sorcery - while not condoned by the Church - are quite present in indigenous Catholicism and spirituality. Most often, it is associated with healing, natural medicine, childbirth, and female power. However, sorcery for evil is also present.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Particular since indigenous communities are often governed by a council of elders who advise the rotating roles of elected community leaders, respect of elders is quite important.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly within EAPI, a strand of indigenous Catholicism that emerged out of Liberation Theology, economic fairness is of utmost importance. Similar to the work of Christian Base Communities, the abolition of exploitation is a long term goal of indigenous Catholic activists, and many view capitalism and neoliberalism as the sources of sin in the modern world.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Not really. For the most part, in the Catholic sense, god and the saints are understood to be good, if occasionally fickle. Punishment, in the eyes of popular and indigenous Catholics most often consists of a saint's refusal to intercede in everyday life on behalf of the petitioner or devotee. Refusal to do so is understood to be the result of insufficient devotion, prayer, or offering. In other words, the relationship between saint and human is transactional.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: Rewards are, in the Catholic sense of saints as intercessors, in return for devotion, prayer, offering, and attention given to the particular saint or image that the devotee is appealing to for help or aid.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Again, among indigenous Catholics, the Catholic notions of heaven/hell, and the rituals required (baptism, confession) in order to ascend to heaven, are powerful. In some communities, baptism has been conceived of as the "ticket" to heaven.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: Good luck, but not luck as random chance. Perhaps rewards should best be conceived of as good fortune in the sector or issue for which devotees are requesting the aid of saints and intercessors.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: For rural indigenous Catholics, patron saints of agriculture are of particular importance.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: As national and international migration have become facts of life for indigenous communities across Mexico, patron saints of migrants and journeys have ascended to

high importance for many individuals, families, and communities.

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - No
- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes
- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - No
- ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Jesus Christ is the messiah in Christianity. His second coming will bring about the end of this age on earth and cast judgment (send to heaven or hell) those who are alive.

Notes: Although some Christian messianic beliefs revolve around the end of the age and the final judgment, indigenous Catholicisms connected to EAPI (with considerable liberationist influence) tend to regard the coming of Christ as the time when the kingdom of Heaven shall be built upon the earth. In other popular and indigenous Christianities, involvements of other saints and holy figures in millenarian and messianic beliefs revolve around a purification of the earth, a wiping away of evil - sometimes imagined as the oppressors and the structures of oppression.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Indigenous Catholicism, as promoted by EAPI, tends to be both past and future oriented. In relation to its liberationist influences and Liberation Theology's conceptualization of sin as a social problem, religiously-motivated activism to address the social sins of oppression, injustice, and inequality can and potentially will usher in a new world in which the Kingdom of Heaven is built on Earth. However, this new era is also deeply influenced and shaped by the past - an imagined return to precolonial social relations that existed in imagined harmony of kinship and "comunalidad" without the oppression of the colonizers.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Potentially depending on the addressing of the social sins of oppression, inequality, and injustice.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: A restoration of harmonic community living as imagined to have existed prior to the colonial conquest of the Americas.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is perhaps one of the most important elements of EAPI's work and indigenous Catholicisms more broadly. The social norms promoted by EAPI are related to the meaning of living in indigenous community and the rights and responsibilities entailed by community membership. In addition to cultural and linguistic revitalization, community norms include respect for elders, community service in ascending importance within the civil/religious "cargos" system, and periodic unpaid community labor on civil and religious infrastructure for collective benefit (road repair, church repair, school construction, for example). Indigenous intellectuals in southern Mexico have conceptualized these collective actions geared toward maintaining community under the umbrella term of "comunalidad," imperfectly translated as communality, or the ways of being of and in community. EAPI, in its promotion of best practices in indigenous ministry and indigenous Catholicism, places profound importance on ideas of community, service, and community membership and participation.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: This distinction, at times, runs contrary to the teachings of the institutional Catholic Church. Or at the very least, EAPI recognizes (and promotes sometimes) a pragmatism with regards to Catholic moral teachings. For instance, in 2016, while the Mexican Catholic Church was mobilizing public protests against same-sex marriage, EAPI was obligated to address homosexuality and marriage in their annual meetings. EAPI's meeting conclusions stressed that issues of sexual orientation and partnership are secondary to the obligations and responsibilities of indigenous community membership. Similarly, indigenous Catholicisms often invest more religious authority in lay members (and increasingly, in women) than in clergy whose presence in communities is often sporadic because of the realities of terrain, distance, and small rural population centers.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

– All individuals within contemporary world

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly in relation to "comunalidad," or being in community.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: But this is often unenforced

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: This is of utmost importance for EAPI and indigenous Catholicisms, the cooperation that community membership entails.

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: The idea of "comunalidad." All of the elements, the rights and responsibilities, of indigenous community membership.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Clergy, priests and nuns, do take vows of celibacy. It is estimated, however, that a slight majority of priests working in rural, and particularly southern and indigenous, Mexico may be involved in (generally heterosexual) sexual unions. The dynamics of community membership and the importance placed on family has rendered priestly sexual partnerships a largely irrelevant question in much of indigenous Mexico and certain parishes have expressed preference for married priests. See, for example, Emiliano Ruiz Parra, "Ovejas Negras: Rebeldes de la iglesia mexicana en el siglo XXI." Other clergy, priests and nuns, have renounced their vows and have continued working in and with indigenous communities as lay religious and activist leaders.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Although the Catholic Church and other Christian churches have clear teachings on sexual activity - no sex before/outside of marriage, no homosexual sex - these are generally of secondary importance to EAPI and indigenous Catholicisms that are focused predominantly on culture, community, and preservation of indigenous religious traditions. The reality of everyday life, even as much of indigenous Mexico tends toward social and sexual conservatism, recognizes a pragmatism of partnerships and relationships.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: The sacrifice, or outlay, of personal and familial resources toward community projects - infrastructural, governmental, and religious - is functionally required for community membership in many indigenous communities. Those who have refused to contribute to community endeavors, often because of conversion to evangelical and pentecostal churches, have sparked considerable community backlash throughout indigenous Mexico.

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Involvement in community and parish activities related to indigenous religious and cultural preservation is key to EAPI's continued existence.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: At times, yes. Some EAPI members are active in land and territorial defense activism for indigenous communities against large state projects (hydroelectric dams in particular) and extractive industries.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: However, throughout indigenous Mexico, violence and harassment against converts to evangelical Christianity and pentecostalism is not uncommon due to their refusal to contribute to community projects deemed essential for community membership. While this has abated over time, it is still present. EAPI's formal stance is one of nonviolence and ecumenism.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 500

Notes: Could be hundreds or thousands - depends on the size of the community celebrating a patron saint festival.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 1

Notes: 1 Year, patron saint celebrations tend to be the largest ritual celebrations. EAPI views the patron saint festival as one of the foundational elements of community cohesion

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: However, patron saint festivals certainly change over time

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: However, patron saint festivals certainly change over time

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Alcohol, in most cases, although hallucinogens are still used in some indigenous communities and religious rituals despite teachings from the Catholic Church against their use.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Indigenous Catholics of EAPI both have their own indigenous conceptions of fictive kinship revolving around community participation and membership and the common Christian fictive kinship relations of brotherhood and sisterhood.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: There are similar organizations throughout the Latin American Catholic Churches dedicated to indigenous ministry and indigenous Catholicisms, but EAPI is only made up of Mexican members and is correspondingly affiliated with the Episcopal Conference of Mexico (Conferencia del Episcopado Mexicano).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as group members have mobilized to help communities stricken by natural disasters (earthquakes, hurricanes, flooding), they have done so not necessarily as EAPI but as active lay Catholics and inspired by liberationist currents within the Church.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the world of Catholic charities, Caritas is the organization sponsored and organized the Episcopate. Catholic Relief Services also operates in Mexico and throughout Latin America. There are a wide range of Catholic, Christian, and secular organizations (national and international) that provide famine and natural disaster relief.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although perhaps not as EAPI. Many EAPI members are involved in additional groups, organizations, and activities connected to the Catholic Church, some of which engage in poverty relief, mutual aid, and meeting basic needs of community members in need.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Same as above on famine relief - there are a wide range of state, Church, and non-state organizations operating in Mexico that EAPI members and indigenous Catholics may receive aid from. However, rural and indigenous poverty remains a persistent problem, indicating that such aid has not yet achieved widespread poverty relief.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: While EAPI itself does not provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm, the Catholic Church often does. Community members in need of institutionalized care for themselves or family members may avail themselves of Church affiliated care options.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: EAPI does not operate formal educational institutions although the Catholic Church certainly does (from preschool through university). However, education is perhaps one of the primary goals of EAPI. Its programming often consists of historical and anthropological exploration of indigenous cultural and religious practices, and group meetings are centered around discussion of indigeneity, religion, and how to interpret reality through the scripture and the scripture through the indigenous reality.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to Catholic educational institutions, public schooling in Mexico has expanded to nearly every corner of the country and even the most remote indigenous communities generally have access to at least primary schooling.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The EAPI organizing committee, mostly made up of clergy, answers to the Mexican Episcopate, and they are in charge of organizing annual regional and national meetings. However, within parish and diocesan EAPI groups, there is little in the way of formal bureaucracy.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexican Episcopate and the institutional Catholic Church.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Group members may be involved in agricultural cooperatives, however.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Group members may be involved in community water management, but that is not officially connected to their roles within EAPI. However, EAPI's mission to promote communal governance practices according to indigenous community governance traditions has surely influenced the ways in which some communities have organized assemblies and committees to manage drinking water and irrigation.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Occasionally the state government is involved, but rural water management tends to be a municipal responsibility.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: However, group members certainly have engaged in activism to pressure state institutions to construct and maintain roads that connect rural communities to market centers.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In many indigenous communities and indigenous municipalities, policing is a rotational duty for community members in their ascent up the community governance hierarchy. Otherwise, in larger municipalities, there may be professional police forces.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexican federal, state, and municipal governments operate the judicial system. However, in some indigenous communities, low level offenses may be dealt with in community assembly.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Same as the judicial system, operated by the Mexican State. However, in some indigenous communities, low level offenses dealt with in community assembly may enforce punishments more geared toward restorative justice.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Mexico abolished the death penalty in 2005.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexican legal code

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. There are certainly indigenous Catholics enlisted in the Mexican military forces, but EAPI does not necessarily encourage enlistment.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexican Armed Forces

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to Spanish, EAPI members (particularly clergy) have been heavily involved in creating indigenous language translations of Catholic liturgy and biblical texts. In 2013, the Vatican authorized Nahuátl as a legitimate liturgical language and tasked the Mexican episcopate with formalizing a translation of biblical and liturgical texts. Although there are a number of protestant translations of the bible into indigenous languages and dialects, particularly those undertaken in the 20th century by the Summer Institute of Linguistics, these are rejected in favor of working toward a singular translation that would be mutual intelligible across Nahuátl dialects. Similar projects are in the works among indigenous Catholics and EAPI members in other linguistic zones of Mexico, including Mazatec, Mixtec, Zapotec, Maya, and others. These projects have been aided by gradual expansion of bilingual indigenous/Spanish public educational programs (particularly since the 1970s) and the indigenous cultural resurgence of the 1980s and 90s that have seen formalization of indigenous written languages and publication of indigenous-language literature.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See comments on previous answer

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Catholic liturgical and feast day calendar is used across the Catholic world and EAPI is no exception. However, among different indigenous groups there are also precolonial indigenous calendars (the Maya cylindrical calendars, for example) that EAPI promotes recognition of and adherence to. These different calendrical systems are not understood by EAPI members to be contradictory, but rather exist as integrated and combined structures of religious practice. Since the colonial era, syncretic indigenous Catholicisms certainly preserved some elements of indigenous religious celebrations in the guise of (or transferred to) Catholic ritual celebration. EAPI advocates that the indigenous roots and heritage of these practices is more fully recognized and acknowledged as practices that preceded and survived the conquest.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The liturgical and feast day calendar is set by the Roman Catholic Church.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Due to the complicated legal and constitutional legacy of the Mexican Revolution, many indigenous communities still have lands held in common. This is known as the ejido. However, that does not always mean that common lands are worked in common - many of them are divided between heads of households of the particular community. Yet, many communities designate a portion of ejidal lands to be worked in common and agricultural production dedicated to a specific purpose, generally to support the patron saint feast day festivities. The lack of uniformity among ejidal arrangements makes it difficult to generalize practices across indigenous Mexico, but the ejido (and common land) is of prime importance to EAPI and the idea of comunalidad, or being in community.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: EAPI members are certainly involved in capitalist agricultural networks, both as producers and consumers, connected to national and international markets. Similar to the ejido, EAPI also advocates for the formation of producer and consumer cooperatives.

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